

AVEDHYA SIRA: CLINICAL AND ANATOMICAL RELEVANCE IN AYURVEDIC PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Ayurvedic texts described anatomical perspective of *Sira* especially in context to *Sharira Sthana*. The structure, distribution, and functional relevance of *Sira* in the human body are all thoroughly explained by Ayurveda. The four main categories of *Sira* are *Aruna*, *Sweta*, *Lohita*, and *Neela*, each of which is connected to a different *Dosha*. *Saran Kriya* is the characteristic that allows blood to flow via these veins. *Sira* are further separated into *Vedhya Sira* and *Avedhya Sira* based on their vulnerability to puncturing during therapeutic operations. There are 602 *Vedhya Sira* and 98 are *Avedhya Sira* in human body. In general veins and arteries that shouldn't be punctured during *Raktamokshana* therapy are referred to as *Avedhya Sira*. Puncturing *Avedhya Sira* is strictly forbidden due to the possibility of serious or even deadly repercussions, *Vedhya Sira* can be pierced therapeutically during treatments such as *Raktamokshana*. Before undergoing venesection Identification and knowledge about *Avedhya Sira* is very important to avoid complications such as severe bleeding, loss of sensation, deformity, or death. This article emphasizes clinical and anatomical relevance of *Avedhya Sira* in Ayurvedic practice.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Avedhya Sira*, *Venesection*, *Sira*, *Raktamokshana*.**INTRODUCTION**

The intricate system of veins and arteries that carry blood and other essential nutrients throughout the body is represented by the Ayurvedic notion of *Sira*, or vessels. Due to its considerable therapeutic effectiveness in a variety of ailments, *Sushruta* referred to *Sira Vedhana* as *Ardha Chikitsa*. However, because of the potential for serious consequences like profuse bleeding, paralysis, tissue necrosis, and even death, puncturing particular vessels known as *Avedhya Sira* is strictly forbidden. The *Sushruta Samhita*'s vast anatomical knowledge is reflected in the idea of *Avedhya Sira*, which is a key element of Ayurvedic surgery.^[1-3]

Sira mainly refers to veins that transport polluted blood to the heart, especially *Neela Sira*. *Sira* originated in the *Nabhi*, from which they propagated throughout the body. These vessels are also known as *Sarvavaha* because they carry *Doshas* and other body fluids. *Sira Vedhana* is a significant therapeutic treatment that falls under the *Raktamokshana* category. It involves the removal of

unclean blood and vitiated *Doshas* in order to treat a variety of illnesses. In order to provide therapeutic advantage, particular *Sira* are punctured based on the disease situation.^[4-6]

Anatomical Aspects of Avedhya Sira

There are 602 *Vedhya Sira* and 98 *Avedhya Sira* among the 700 *Sira* listed in Ayurveda. Understanding these *Avedhya Sira* is crucial during *Sira Vedhana* since an unintentional puncture could create major problems. Therefore, before undertaking venesection treatments, Ayurvedic emphasizes the importance of having a thorough understanding of anatomy.

The 98 *Avedhya Sira* is found throughout the body. There are striking parallels between the Ayurvedic description of *Avedhya Sira* and contemporary anatomical concepts of essential blood vessels, arteries, veins, and neurovascular structures that need to be protected during surgical procedures. Therefore, comprehending *Avedhya Sira* from both traditional and

contemporary viewpoints may help with safer clinical procedures and accurate surgery.^[5-7]

Avedhya Sira must be properly preserved during treatments like *Raktamokshana* since damage to them

during *Sira Vedhana* may result in serious consequences. These vessels are distributed throughout three major anatomical regions of the body: *Shakha*, *Koshtha* and *Jatrurdhwa* or *Urdhvajatrugata* region. The regional distribution of *Avedhya Sira* are mentioned in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Distribution of *Avedhya Sira*.

There are 104 *Vedhya Sira* and 32 *Avedhya Sira* in the *Koshtha*. Similar to this, 50 *Sira* are categorized as *Avedhya Sira* and 114 *Sira* are *Vedhya* in the *Jatrurdhwa* or *Urdhvajatrugata* region. Thirty-two of the 98 *Avedhya Sira* is found in the *Koshtha* region, fifty in the head and neck region, and sixteen in the extremities. The *Urdhvajatrugata* region's high prevalence of *Avedhya Sira* suggests the existence of extremely important anatomical structures there, where an unintentional puncture could result in potentially fatal consequences. Ayurvedic scriptures also link these *Avedhya Sira* to significant anatomical features and stress that incorrect puncturing can lead to consequences like profuse bleeding, loss of function, deformity, unconsciousness, paralysis, and even death. Thus, before performing *Sira Vedhana*, a thorough understanding of anatomy was thought to be necessary. The modern concept that major arteries, veins, and neurovascular bundles must be preserved during surgical procedures is very similar to the classical description of *Avedhya Sira*.^[6-8]

Clinical Significance & Modern Relevance of *Avedhya Sira*

The *Sushruta Samhita*'s description of *Avedhya Sira* exemplifies Ayurveda's sophisticated anatomical and surgical knowledge. These explanations strongly align with contemporary philosophy of major veins, arteries, and neurovascular bundles that need to be protected during surgical procedures. As a result, understanding *Avedhya Sira* is still crucial for safe surgical and

parasurgical treatments, especially when performing *Raktamokshana* and *Sira Vedhana*.

Jaldhara, *Urvi* and *Lohitaksha* are significant *Avedhya Sira* in the extremes. *Jaldhara* is associated with the great saphenous vein in the lower limb and the cephalic vein in the upper limb. Puncturing these arteries could cause significant blood loss because they are in charge of draining blood from the dorsal venous arch. The brachial and femoral vessels are represented by *Urvi*, and damage to these vessels might result in severe bleeding and even death. *Lohitaksha*, also known as "*Lohitakshayen Maranam*" in Ayurveda, is linked to the profunda femoris vessels in the lower limb and the axillary vessels in the upper limb, where puncturing may result in significant blood loss.^[7-9]

Vitapa, *Katiktaruna*, *Parshva*, *Pristha*, *Udara*, and *Vaksha* are among the *Avedhya Sira* in the *Koshtha* region. Necrosis of the gonads can result from damage to the testicular and ovarian vessels, which are connected to *Vitapa Sira*. *Katiktaruna* is associated with gluteal vessels, which can be punctured to cause gluteal muscular necrosis. Injuries to *Parshva Sira*, which are located along the lateral thoracoabdominal area, may result in severe bleeding and poor drainage. *Pristha Sira* is associated with subscapular vessels, and puncturing them can result in blood loss, paralysis, and nerve damage. If damaged, *Udara Sira*, which correlates to epigastric vessels, may cause profuse bleeding. Cardiac function may be negatively impacted by puncturing

Vaksha Sira, which include the coronary, internal mammary, intercostal, and lateral thoracic arteries.^[6-8]

Due to the presence of important neurovascular structures in the head and neck, the *Urdhwajatrugata* region has the highest number of *Avedhya Sira*. Because *Marma Sangya Sira* are connected to the jugular veins and internal and external carotid arteries, damage to these vessels might result in potentially fatal consequences. Occipital vessels are associated with *Krikatika Sira*, whereas post-auricular vessels are associated with *Vidhura Sira*. Puncturing either of these vessels can result in serious consequences. Internal maxillary vessels are known as *Sandhidhamani Sira*, and damage to them can cause *Manyastambha*, or stiff neck. Necrosis of the tongue might result from puncturing *Rasavahe* and *Vagvahe Sira*, which are linked to profunda linguae vessels. *Aupanasika Sira* are angular vessels located in little's area of the nose, where damage can cause severe epistaxis. *Apanga Sira* is connected to the zygomaticotemporal artery and, if destroyed, might result in blindness or vision problems. Tympanic and posterior auricular vessels connected to sensitive auditory areas are included in *Shabdavahini Sira*. Injuries to the superficial vessels of the scalp and cranial region such as *Kesanugata*, *Sthapani*, *Utkshepa*, *Avarta*, *Adhipati Sira* and *Simanta*, may result in significant bleeding, poor scalp drainage, and other consequences.^[7-10]

Modern View

Ayurveda describes a number of vessels that are closely related to significant veins and arteries identified in contemporary medicine. For instance, the great saphenous vein and the cephalic vein are important superficial veins; puncturing of these vessels could result in serious bleeding. *Sushruta's* description of the consequences of puncturing *Avedhya Sira* is very similar to contemporary vascular and neurological issues.^[7, 8]

CONCLUSION

Sushruta wrote about *Sira* describes *Aruna*, *Neela*, *Shweta*, and *Lohita* as the four forms of *Sira* that correspond to *Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*, and *Rakta*, respectively. Certain anatomical locations have been identified for the safe execution of venesection (*Sira Vedhana*) which is a significant therapeutic technique employed in the treatment of numerous illnesses. Ayurveda also describes the concept of *Avedhya Sira*, or vessels that should never be pierced because damage to these structures might result in serious difficulties and, in some situations, even death. 98 of the 700 *Sira* that have been identified in the human body are categorized as *Avedhya Sira*. These are further divided into three distinct anatomical regions: *Urdhwajatrugata*, *Koshthagata*, and *Shakhagata*. There are fifty *Avedhya Sira* in the head and neck region, thirty-two in the *Koshtha* region, and sixteen at the extremities. Essential *Avedhya Sira* in the upper limb are *Jaaldhara*, *Urvi* and *Lohitaksha*; in the lower limb, these correspond with

essential vascular structures including the femoral vein, femoral artery, and saphenous vein. Puncturing these deep veins can cause severe bleeding, tissue injury, paralysis, or other significant problems since they are closely linked to important structures. Therefore Ayurvedic scriptures emphasize how important it is to recognize and safeguard *Avedhya Sira* during the processes such as *Sira Vedhana*.

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